

MANGROVE AS AN ECONOMIC MOVER BASED ON CULTURE AND LOCAL WISDOM IN SEMANTING BAY, BERAU DISTRICT

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Abstract

Teluk Semanting Village, Berau Regency, one of the keys to the success of mangrove conservation and at the same time a potential factor for the sustainability and competitiveness of the mangrove tourist village destination is the local wisdom of the local community. Local wisdom should be the key to implementing sustainable tourism villages which have an impact on sustainable mangrove development. The aim of the research is to determine the implications of the cultural dimensions and local wisdom of the mangrove ecotourism village in empowering the economic community in Teluk Semanting Village, Berau Regency. Data collection techniques are observation and conducting interviews. The analysis technique used is descriptive qualitative. The research results show that the strategy for developing mangrove ecotourism is to innovate, improve and increase mangrove planting, increase cooperation between the government and other institutions, create opportunities for creative economic income from the community, improve facilities and infrastructure, provide counseling and education for the community and managers, involve community participation., and apply the rules. In addition, local cultural values can guide the development of tourism activities that respect traditions and create economic opportunities for local communities. In managing mangrove ecotourism, it is important to respect and integrate local wisdom in long-term management plans.

Keywords: Mangrove Ecotourism, Economy, Culture and Local Wisdom.

1. INTRODUCTION

Local Wisdom, Every country in the world has its own uniqueness, including Indonesia. Our country is so unique, so unique that if there was a nomination for the most unique country, then Indonesia would definitely be included as one of the nominees, in fact, it might even come out as the champion. Unfortunately, as time goes by, just like most customs, traditions and culture, the local wisdom that exists in various regions is increasingly being eroded by time. It is rare to find a region maintaining local wisdom that has been handed down from its ancestors, with changing times replacing it with views from outside which may not necessarily be true or will only damage existing local wisdom. The uniqueness of Indonesia itself comes from the customs, traditions and local wisdom that exist in Indonesia. Not just one, each region even has its own local wisdom.

Local wisdom can also be understood as cultural identity. This matter in line with Soebadio's explanation (1986: 18-19) in Sobarna, et al (2019: 18) that the local genius who is currently famous for his cultural identity is a cultural identity or personality of a nation, which results in that The nation in question becomes better able to absorb and process influences culture that comes to him from outside his own region, according to his character and personal needs.

The people of Semanting Bay are still steeped in customs and culture has existed since ancient times as an ancestral tradition. Traditional rituals especially at the time of dropping off a new

boat and the custom of entering a new house from scratch Until the end, it is still often done by the community. Mutual cooperation is something that is very noticeable, especially when there are village activities, for example work devotion.

Community empowerment as a strategy to improve welfare of society or improving the quality of society must pay attention to or understand the condition of society, including the assets in it inside. Because the assets that exist in society can become advantages which can be developed for the welfare of society. There are no assets either become a problem or obstacle for society to improve quality his life. Through community empowerment, assets that do not yet exist can be obtained important to society important to develop or create for help people improve their quality of life. For example, somewhere A village where the majority of the population lives from agriculture. But in the village the capital or physical assets are inadequate, such as roads or bridges, so It is very difficult for people to market their agricultural products. This is one examples where these assets are very important.

Semanting Bay Village has a lot of good potential in terms of resources nature, marine resources, capture fisheries and ecotourism areas. Region Ecotourism will have an impact on local communities such as increasing income, increased employment opportunities and business opportunities. Along With the development of ecotourism activities, many domestic and foreign tourists come to enjoy the beauty of the natural panorama. Visitors coming very influential on the income of local communities. This is because Visitors who come to the area will spend some of their money towards ecotourism activities. so as to develop ecotourism areas will affect the economic activities of local communities in that area. If the development of the ecotourism area goes according to plan, then local communities in the area do not feel disadvantaged because it will help in improving a better lifestyle.

Assets that exist in the community or are owned by the community plays a very important role in the process of community empowerment and development. For example, in the process of community empowerment the role of human assets is very important support the continued development or empowerment of capacity or community capabilities. But in this case the role of other assets is also very important role. For example, to increase human assets, physical assets such as: schools or hospitals as a means to develop knowledge, expertise, education and public health. Likewise with assets Finance really supports society to improve its economy.

Social assets as a means of developing social ties or social networks in meeting people's needs. Apart from that, capital or environmental and technological assets are very important in helping Society to develop its natural resources with the assistance of mastery of technology that can increase the use of natural resources existing in society such as the use of technology for development community farming so that it can improve community welfare.

Semanting Bay Mangrove Ecotourism, Berau Regency which has uniqueness, it can be utilized as a potential natural resource to be used as an ecotourism area. An effort to utilize resources The optimal local option is to develop tourism with a concept ecotourism. The implementation of an ecotourism system in the mangrove ecosystem is an approach to sustainable use of the ecosystem.

Activity Ecotourism is an effective alternative to overcome problems environment in ecosystems, such as excessive levels of exploitation by society in creating economic alternatives for society in particular coastal communities in Teluk Semanting village, Berau Regency. Activity Ecotourism cannot be separated or cannot be separated from these efforts mangrove conservation, local economic empowerment with mutual respect cultural or cultural differences. Shifting the concept of world tourism to a model ecotourism.

The development of mangrove ecotourism can be considered as a step strategy to answer these demands. By 2023, ecotourism sustainability not only looking at environmental aspects, but also involving cultural elements and local wisdom in efforts to empower the local community's economy. Involving the community directly in development and management Ecotourism destinations are considered the key to achieving that balance between economic prosperity and environmental sustainability. Importance Mangrove ecotourism in sustainable development is also reflected in the views of a number of ecotourism and environmental experts.

Dr. Martha Honey (2008), an ecotourism expert, stated that successful ecotourism must covers three main dimensions: environmental, economic, and social. In this case, Mangrove ecotourism in Kampung Teluk Semanting is directed to provide positive impact on environmental conservation, community economic empowerment local, and preservation of cultural heritage. In 2019, Prof. Dr. Steve McCool, an expert in ecotourism and resort management, emphasizes the importance of understanding local wisdom and applying it in ecotourism development. Integration Local wisdom, according to McCool, does not only produce tourist experiences that is more authentic but also supports the well-being of local communities.

Culture-based approach in developing mangrove ecotourism also in line with the views of Prof. Dr. Dallen J. Timothy (2011), who emphasizes the need to embrace local culture as the main attraction of the destination tour. According to Timothy, ecotourism destinations are successfully taking advantage Local wisdom and maintaining traditional culture can build connections emotionally with tourists, increasing the attractiveness of the destination, and on finally achieve economic sustainability.

Based on the description above, this research will develop a research gap with a design for developing sustainable mangrove ecotourism based on studies regarding culture and local wisdom for developing ecotourism in a region that have been carried out both across countries and in Indonesia.

In this research, it is still rare to find anything related to the development of mangrove ecosystems by paying attention to cultural concepts and local wisdom in developing the surrounding economy, so this panel aims to identify internal and external factors in the community in increasing business and preserving the mangroves of Semanting Bay, Berau Regency and formulating appropriate strategies. right to achieve its goal of developing sustainable mangrove ecotourism based on local culture and wisdom in empowering the people of Kampung Teluk Semanting, Berau Regency.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Ecotourism, Principles and Policies

Based on the two words eco and tourism, which when adopted into Indonesian became the words eco and tourism or eco and tourism. The basic meaning of these two words can be explained as follows, eco, which in Greek means home, and tourism, which means tour or journey. In essence, the definition of ecotourism is a form of tourism that is responsible for preserving natural areas, provides economic benefits and maintains cultural integrity for local communities. Ecotourism as an alternative economic activity in natural areas is expected to be a tool for a conservation approach, respecting nature more and utilizing nature without destroying it. Ecotourism is able to create many new jobs and become a new source of livelihood. Local people can become local tour guides, home stay providers, handicraft or souvenir makers, or managers of ecotourism areas. You can also get involved management of local indigenous cultural attractions, for example as a dancer, traditional clothing tailor, weaver, etc.

According to Page and Ross (2002), ecotourism consists of three main principles, namely; conservation principles, community participation principles and economic principles. Meanwhile, according to Damanik and Weber (2006), there are principles that must be fulfilled in developing ecotourism, namely: 1) Reducing negative impacts in the form of damage or pollution to the environment and local culture due to tourism activities; 2) Building awareness and respect for the environment and providing cultural benefits in tourist destinations, both for tourists, local communities and other tourism actors; 3) Offer positive experiences for tourists in maintenance and conservation; 4) Providing direct financial benefits for conservation purposes through extra tourism contributions or expenditures; 5) Provide financial benefits and empowerment for local communities; 6) Creating tourism products that prioritize local values; 7) Increase sensitivity to the social, environmental and political situation in tourist destination areas; 8) Respect human rights and work agreements, in the sense of giving freedom to tourists and local communities to enjoy tourist attractions as a form of human rights, as well as complying with fair and mutually agreed rules of play in implementation tourism transactions.

In developing ecotourism, the regulations that apply in a particular place will of course be taken into account, for example in nature conservation forest areas, protected forests or production forests. The provisions that must be met so as not to violate regulations in building facilities and infrastructure are very important. Some of these laws and regulations will be presented as follows: 1) Law Number 5 of 1990 concerning Conservation of Biological Resources and Ecosystems to Support Community Welfare and Quality of Life; 2) Law Number 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry; 3) Law Number 7 of 2004 concerning Resource Management

Water power; 4) Law Number 25 of 2004 concerning the National Development Planning System; 5) Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government as amended by Law Number 12 of 2008; 6) Law Number 26 of 2007 concerning Spatial Planning; 7) Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism.

2.2 Mangrove Ecosystem

Mangrove is a combination of the word mangal from Portuguese and the word grove from English. In Portuguese, the word mangrove is used for individual types of plants and the word mangal for forest communities consisting of individual types of mangroves. Meanwhile, in English, the word mangrove is used both for communities of trees or grass and shrubs that grow in the sea as well as for individual plant species associated with them (Macnae, 1968). The mangrove ecosystem is a habitat for a variety of flora and fauna, many of which are very unique and their existence depends on the mangrove ecosystem. Mangroves play an important role in moving organic materials and energy from land ecosystems to aquatic ecosystems. Biologically, the dense roots of mangroves are habitat for various living creatures, ranging from fish, crabs, shrimp and mollusks. These roots also provide a function for maintaining small fish to grow to maturity so they can be consumed by humans. Mangroves are breeding places for various migratory birds and local birds in the mangrove area.

Mangroves are a habitat for reptiles, amphibians and mammals. Mangroves are a productive ecosystem and make a major contribution to combating global warming. Physically, mangroves play a function in protecting coastal land from the threat of sea water which can erode land. Mangroves play a role in protecting beaches from rising sea levels due to global warming which is currently underway. The role of mangroves is globally recognized by researchers, governments and the world community so that the mangrove conservation movement is currently receiving appreciation and support from various parties (Valiela et al., 2001; Saenger, 2002; Mmom & Arokoyu, 2010). Mangrove forests are also very necessary for the population of fish, shrimp and crab species as well as pond cultivation cultivated by fishermen and pond farmers.

2.3 Economic development of coastal communities

The reason for the importance of coastal economic management goals is that ecological economics examines the relationship between ecosystems, the economy, and human welfare. This can be said to be one of the fastest growing areas in the economic field. Sweeden et al (2008) stated that understanding coastal economics provides an important economic contribution from ecosystems to the economy for several reasons. First, coastal ecosystems are very productive and contribute a large amount of economic value to the coastal economy. Second, all countries in general, and coastal economies in particular, have complex systems of property, markets, productive organizations, Arifin (2004:6) states that co-management combines elements of the user community (fishermen's groups, fisheries entrepreneurs, etc.) and the government which avoids an excessively dominant role from one party in managing coastal and marine resources so that the biased aspirations of one party can be eliminated. In the long term, the implementation of co-management is believed to provide changes for the better, namely: 1) increasing public awareness of the importance of coastal and marine resources in supporting life, 2) increasing community capacity, so that they are able to participate in every stage integrated management, 3) increasing community income with sustainable and environmentally friendly forms of use

2.4 Sustainable Development Concept for Better Use of Natural Resources

Development is an activity of all communities and nations in the world to improve human welfare. Development thus utilizes various existing natural resources for human welfare. Sustainable development is one of the choices of the global community, where modern development seeks positive changes in better socio-economic and environmental aspects. According to experts, the successful implementation of sustainable development in various regions requires synergy of planning, policy and support from the community and stakeholders. (Chichilnisky, 1997; Bass, S., & Dalal-Clayton, 2012).

According to the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987) Sustainable Development is a development vision that seeks to meet the needs of the present without disrupting the ability of future generations to meet their needs. Sustainable development has placed environmental preservation policies as a necessity in economic development. In other words, environmental preservation policy is one of the constant variables in the economic development process of a nation. The principles of sustainable development are actually simple, not complex and easy to understand. This is based on the fact that the level of economic growth has limits and an economy that relies on the extraction of natural resources does not last long.

Natural resources should be managed sustainably as a basis for improving human welfare and economic activity. Thus, it has been globally agreed that the development of natural resources must consider three aspects at once, namely economic, ecological and social. In line with this, efforts to change unsustainable consumption and production patterns are the main thing to support efforts to protect the carrying capacity of ecosystems and environmental functions as a prerequisite for improving community welfare (Rees, 1992, Munasinghe, 1993)

2.5 Cultural Values and Local Wisdom in Community Empowerment through Ecotourism Development

Culture itself is defined as collective subjectivity (Casson, 1992). Subjectivity has two meanings in economics. The Subjective Theory of Value emphasizes that an individual's preferences cannot be measured and are only indirectly reflected in that individual's behavior.

The moral aspect of culture will influence preferences, while the technical aspect of culture will influence beliefs (Casson, 1992). Although these two aspects are differentiated, these aspects are related to each other. The moral aspect of culture includes group habits that will encourage a person's behavior to treat people better, such as honesty, integrity, and so on. This will improve coordination the decisions of different individuals will ultimately reduce transaction costs. For example, if we know that a person is honest and has integrity, it will be easier for us to trust him so that it will be easier for us to carry out transactions with that person. Thus, this behavior can encourage the efficiency of the group. In addition to lowering transaction costs, the impact of the moral aspect on efficiency also compensates for lost ownership rights. This is related to the possibility of having important jobs, but which do not

provide sufficient material rewards. The culture may instill moral values into these jobs so that there are still people willing to do the work. On the other hand, the technical aspect of culture is a habit that encourages a person's behavior to further build an environment that supports efficiency, such as hard work, respect for time, and so on. This can support technological improvements through innovation so that the efficiency of the group can increase. As is known, the performance of a group is not only related to efficiency, but also related to justice (equity). When it is related to justice, it turns out that the moral aspect of culture speaks more (Casson, 1992).

Local wisdom can be understood as local ideas that are wise, full of wisdom, of good value, which are embedded and followed by community members (Sartini, 2004). Local wisdom is actually the result of local community intelligence (local genius) in interacting with the surrounding environment. Local genius is a local identity or national cultural identity which causes the nation to be able to absorb and process foreign culture according to its own character and abilities. Moendardjito, as quoted by Sartini, said that regional cultural elements have the potential to become local geniuses because they have proven their ability to survive until now (Sartini, 2004). Characteristics include:

- a. able to withstand external cultural influences;
- b. has the ability to accommodate foreign cultural elements;
- c. able to integrate elements of foreign culture into native culture;
- d. have the ability to control;
- e. able to provide direction to cultural development

Forms of local wisdom in society can be in the form of: values, norms, ethics, beliefs, customs, customary laws and special rules. Because it has various forms and lives in various cultures, its functions are varied. Local wisdom has a very broad meaning and function in life, namely:

- a. Serves for the conservation and preservation of natural resources;
- b. Functions for the development of human resources, for example related to life cycle ceremonies;
- c. Functions for the development of culture and science, for example in the Saraswati ceremony, belief and worship at the Panji temple;
- d. Functions as advice, beliefs, literature and taboos;
- e. Socially meaningful, for example communal/kin integration ceremonies;
- f. It has social meaning, for example in agricultural cycle ceremonies
- g. Meaning ethics and morals, which are manifested in the Ngaben ceremony and the purification of ancestral spirits;
- h. Political meaning, for example the ngangkuk merana ceremony and patron-client power (Sartini, 2004)

Thus, the culture of local wisdom funds has an important role in maintaining the identity of the community that owns it and therefore needs to continue to be maintained by passing it on to children and grandchildren because the values contained therein are in accordance with their character and personality.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Types of research

This research uses a qualitative approach with descriptive research type. According to Moleong, descriptive research is defined as research that seeks to reveal a problem and situation as it is, for this reason researchers are limited to only revealing facts and not using hypothesis testing (Moleong, 2002: 6). Thus, this research takes the form of describing, explaining, interpreting problems and then drawing conclusions from these problems regarding the Sustainable Pillar of Economic Empowerment through Mangrove Ecotourism in Semanting Bay, Berau Regency

3.2 Population and Sample

In this research, informants were divided into three groups based on their status and role in forming the direction of Ecotourism development policy based on culture and local wisdom in empowering the community of Teluk Semanting Village, Beru Regency. First, the government group in the executive and legislative (DPRD) which is the group responsible for policy and supervision and regulations in the region to achieve community welfare. Second, community groups which in this case are related to community organizations such as; local/regional communities, external communities or NGOs, and finally academics.

3.3 Technical Data Analysis

This research uses descriptive analysis to determine the implications of the cultural dimensions and local wisdom of the mangrove ecotourism village in empowering the economic community in Teluk Semanting Village, Berau Regency.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The development of mangrove ecotourism in Teluk Semanting Village will empower the community through tourism activities without ignoring the Cultural Dimensions and Local Wisdom. They have worked closely with local communities to document traditional knowledge about the mangrove forest and its surrounding environment. Through active community involvement in tourism design and management, it is ensured that visitors not only understand natural beauty, but also local cultural values and traditions. The use of local guides, arts and traditional crafts in tourism experiences provides additional income to local residents, encourages cultural preservation and sustainably empowers the local economy. Collaboration between the government, community and ecotourism actors is key in creating an immersive and valuable tourism experience for visitors while preserving the cultural heritage of Kampung

Teluk Semanting. In developing mangrove ecotourism in Teluk Semanting village, various aspects of culture and local wisdom can be integrated. Some of these may include Traditional Agricultural Practices, Local Navigational Knowledge, Local Arts and Crafts, Local Food and Drink, Local Ceremonies and Rituals, Locally Based Environmental Education, Knowledge of Local Flora and Fauna, Traditional Music and Performances, Fish Farming and Shellfish Farming, Maritime Cultural Knowledge, Local Stories and Legends, and Local Language and Terms. This integration of cultural aspects and local wisdom will provide an additional dimension to the mangrove ecotourism experience, creating opportunities for tourists to engage deeply with the local community and receive valuable insights into life in Semanting village.

An important aspect in the development and operation of mangrove ecotourism is the participation of local communities through their roles as tour guides, transportation service providers, food or souvenir providers, as well as contributing to educational or cultural activities related to ecotourism. The development of mangrove ecotourism has created employment or business opportunities for local communities, namely as Tour Guides, Management of Homestays and Accommodation, Culinary and Local Food Businesses, Production and Sales of Souvenirs, Transportation Services, Management of Recreational Facilities, Management of Stalls and Restaurants, Farmers and Cultivators, Employment Administrative and Operational, as well as Education and Training. Through the development of mangrove ecotourism, the economic impact of The development of mangrove ecotourism has been felt by the local community. Several training or education programs have also been carried out to strengthen the role of culture and local wisdom in mangrove ecotourism, such as regular dance studio practice and preparation for welcoming visitors. To maintain and protect the mangrove environment during ecotourism development, various proactive steps can be taken. The following are several efforts that can be taken: Preparing Environmental Management Plans, Routine Monitoring and Patrolling, Waste Management, Restricting Tourist Access, Information and Education Boards, Environmental Education, Revegetation and Mangrove Planting, Water and Waste Management, Restricting Destructive Activities, Environmental Monitoring, and Collaborating with Environmental Organizations and Government Institutions. Apart from that, with the existence of mangrove ecotourism, the threat of damage to mangroves from illegal logging around ecotourism areas no longer occurs because indirectly, the presence of managers and visitors prevents illegal logging efforts.

In facing and integrating local culture and wisdom in the development of mangrove ecotourism, there are several specific challenges or problems including maintaining cultural and environmental integrity, Alignment of Values and Priorities, Social and Demographic Changes, Conflicts of Interest, Public Education and Awareness, Regulations and Policies, Participation and Community Involvement, Conflict and Dispute Management, External Influence, Management of Tourist Impacts, and Limited Resources. The development of mangrove ecotourism in Teluk Semanting Village has a direct positive impact on improving the quality of life of the community through increasing income, improving infrastructure and public services, as well as increasing awareness of the importance of the environment and local culture, infrastructure development, increasing access to basic services, developing quality of life and welfare. Social, Community Empowerment, and Long Term Quality of Life

Improvement. Plans for the development or expansion of mangrove ecotourism in the future, and of course this will affect the local community. The plan to develop or expand mangrove ecotourism in the future is expected to have a positive impact on the community in Kampung Teluk Semanting, Berau Regency by creating more economic opportunities through tourism, increasing the income and welfare of the local community, as well as strengthening awareness of the importance of preserving the mangrove environment in the community.

Discussion

According to Indonesian ecotourism observers in Arida (2017), ecotourism is defined as the implementation of responsible tourism activities in natural places and/or areas managed based on natural rules, with the aim of not only enjoying beauty, but also involving elements of education and understanding, and support for nature conservation efforts and improving the welfare of local communities. This definition is then explained in five principles, namely (1) having concern, responsibility and commitment to environmental sustainability; (2) development must be based on deliberation and approval of the local community; (3) provide benefits to local communities; (4) be sensitive to and respect the socio-cultural values and religious traditions held by the local community; and (5) paying attention to laws and regulations in the environmental and tourism sectors (Arida, 2017). The process of developing Mangrove Ecotourism based on Cultural Dimensions and Local Wisdom in Community Economic Empowerment in Teluk Semanting Village, Berau Regency is carried out by collaborating with local communities to document traditional knowledge about mangrove forests and the surrounding environment. Through the active involvement of communities in tourism design and management, they ensure that visitors not only understand the beauty of nature, but also local cultural values and traditions. The use of local guides, traditional arts and crafts, and culinary delights in tourism experiences provides additional income to local residents, encourages cultural preservation, and sustainably empowers local economies.

Collaboration between the government, community and ecotourism actors is key in creating an immersive and valuable tourism experience for visitors while preserving the cultural heritage of Kampung Teluk Semanting. This shows that an important aspect in the development and operation of mangrove ecotourism is the participation of local communities. By empowering local communities as tour guides, handicraft craftsmen, or other service providers, mangrove ecotourism can create economic opportunities and ensure sustainable maintenance of mangrove ecosystems. Apart from that, people can also earn additional income through selling handicraft products and traditional food to tourists. Local communities experience increased income through new employment opportunities in the tourism sector, including tour guiding, local craft sales, and other support services. Apart from that, ecotourism also encourages the growth of local businesses such as homestays, restaurants and souvenir shops. With increased tourist visits, local community income increases, creating a more stable and sustainable economic environment. This success also illustrates the positive impact of ecotourism development on the local economy and empowering local residents financially. In line with Riadhussyah, et al (2021)'s statement that tourism development in villages provides benefits for economic development. Villages that have long been identified with agriculture will

experience a change in the socio-cultural paradigm to become a culture of serving tourists. Providing this tourist service is certainly not easy. In the process of transforming the economic structure, the agricultural sector usually moves from manufacturing to the service sector. By developing tourist villages, the transformation jumps from agriculture directly to services. This is very positive, because the villagers have basically mastered environmental and cultural substances. The next task is to empower village residents with skills and entrepreneurship to provide tourism services and provide satisfaction to visitors. In this way, village residents do not completely depend on the agricultural sector, but also provide tourism services that provide more decent welfare. The face of the village will be filled with tourist service business activities that are profitable (profit orientation) but also socially oriented (non-profit) to support environmental and cultural conservation. Furthermore, village tourism services will also generate economic links and innovation for the birth of processing businesses and other supporting services.

Facing and integrating local culture and wisdom in developing mangrove ecotourism is not easy. There are certain challenges or problems that must be faced. The first challenge concerns Alignment of Values and Priorities, of course local communities may have different values, beliefs or priorities in viewing sustainability and economic interests. Second, there are Social and Demographic Changes, changes in social or demographic structures can influence the way of life and values of local communities. This may require adjusting strategies to ensure the sustainability of ecotourism projects. Third, namely Conflict of Interest, there may be a conflict between economic interests, environmental sustainability and cultural needs. Finding an adequate balance between these three elements can be challenging. Fourth, Education and Public Awareness. Communities may need further education and awareness about the importance of preserving local wisdom and the environment around them. Fifth, Regulations and Policies, namely Regulatory challenges can arise in terms of complying with applicable laws and regulations, including environmental permits, customary land rights, and tourism permits. Sixth, regarding Community Participation and Involvement, namely ensuring that local communities are actively involved in the decision-making process and supporting mangrove ecotourism initiatives is the key to success. Seventh regarding Conflict and Dispute Management, If there are differences of opinion or conflict between the Community or with outside parties, understanding and resolving disputes is an important skill. Eighth, External Influences, namely external factors such as extreme weather changes, market changes, or natural disasters can affect the sustainability of ecotourism projects. Ninth, Management of Tourist Impacts, namely the increasing number of tourists can cause negative impacts on the environment and local culture if not managed well. Lastly Limited Resources, sometimes, limited resources such as funds or personnel can be an obstacle in implementing mangrove ecotourism development initiatives. To overcome these challenges, it is important to involve all stakeholders, pay attention to the needs and aspirations of local communities, and adopt a holistic and sustainable approach in the development of mangrove ecotourism. Apart from that, concrete plans are needed for the development and expansion of mangrove ecotourism in the future. It is hoped that this step will have a positive impact on the community in Teluk Semanting Village, Berau Regency by creating more economic opportunities through tourism,

increasing the income and welfare of the local community, as well as strengthening awareness of the importance of preserving the mangrove environment.

5. CONCLUSION

Local wisdom in Teluk Semanting Village provides valuable lessons in managing mangrove ecotourism. The public can learn about sustainable approaches to the environment, nature conservation, and how to actively involve the community in the management and promotion of ecotourism. In addition, local cultural values can guide the development of tourism activities that respect traditions and create economic opportunities for local communities. In managing mangrove ecotourism, it is important to respect and integrate local wisdom in long-term management plans.

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